

RESEARCH OF THE PROCESSES OCCURRING IN BULK SOILS

Hasanov Davlatbek Davronbek ogli,

Assistant Andijan economy and construction institute

hasanovdavlatbek2@gmail.com

Annotation . This study deals with the preparation of the ground for the construction of buildings and structures in bulk soils, conducting laboratory tests to determine the physical and mechanical properties of bulk soils, natural humidity, density of bulk soils, methods of filling bulk soils, load bearing capacity of the soil. dedicated to determining the ability .

Key words: Specific gravity, bulk soil, self-compaction, amount of subsidence, ground, density of soil, compaction of soil, compaction technology, vibrational compaction, settlement graph, initial moisture .

Physical, physical-chemical, biological and other processes constantly occur in bulk soils, which, on the one hand, lead to their densification and strengthening, on the other hand, to a decrease in strength, deterioration, disintegration of individual particles, i.e. causing particles to form. The self-compaction of bulk soils from specific gravity is considered in section 1.4. The consolidation of bulk soils over time depends on a number of factors, the main of which are: the type of soil, its condition and composition, depending on the method of spilling and compaction, the change of the hydrogeological regime in the composition of the deposit over time, the antiquity of the deposit and

Bulk soils, which are included in natural soils, are usually dominated by hardening processes. Don't go grunt strengthening issue , as well as in general of grunt strength nature the problem solution to do complete not studied .

Research analytical shows that ie clay in grunts connectivity come The output depends on the minerals in melting their on the surface of the Kremengelians colloid shells surface comes , which of particles cementation take will come .

Sandy in grunts quartz particles silica gels with mutually effect result each other with and certain period during known in the circumstances genders to be strengthened take will come . A mountain is a mine industry waste has been reclamation done in the sands reinforcement according to studies take went A few in the remains accumulated waste studied to time come their fruit to be time is 1.5 years and 25 years was Fine particles quartz -glaucinite-phosphate their sands dry in holly density - 1.46 ... 1.52 t / m³ moisture W = 0.142 ... 0.192. Time in Figure 1.2 during reclamation done sands for fortification indicator g_R the change time in - A_t / A_{t_0} , , this on the ground A_t and A_t features or the sands in sensing resistance t - observation period and t_0 – formation during From the graphs apparently as time pass with hardening intensity decreases , a deformation modulus Y_e according to hardening indicators and dynamic to penetration resistance q_d increased goes Under investigation of sands of hardening the most high intensity they are justification starter in the period (t= 2...3 years) hundred gives , , then it slowly slowly decreased goes (t= 3...6 years).

Don't go clay of grunts time during consolidation (hardening) laws , in particular , to sands similar , but that's it with difference does that one different in the circumstances their addiction process and intensity , say Slower . Information available according to of fortification the most big intensity 5...10 years and from him a lot at the time happen will be

Figure 1.2. Reclamation done the sands time during fortification indicator (mining enrichment factory sheds).

Ash and the shapes of the ears time during fortification process , fuel inorganic part thermochemical change as a result formed , enough not studied . Ash and ash of slag physicist and chemical features a lot to factors depends which is they are together most of the time time during resilience and deformation characteristics change laws determination opportunity does not give With that together , partly data identified - ash and ash of slag separately features that's it shows that in general it 's gray beds durability slag and ash to slag relatively much lower : ash collections sheds resilience and deformation characteristics according to so much xar variety old beds new reclamation of those made stronger .

Ash and of slag chemical and physico-minerals composition basically mineral substances of fuel composition determines and that's it changes with , which burning in the process come coming out On average , one different fuel when it burns one from one difference laugh anyway chemical composition long period during practice for enough consider stable can , many in scores important factor this physical - mineral is the composition , therefore because one different

chemical to the contents xar different physical and mineral composition suitable coming can

From this besides , recultivation done ash slag physico-chemical property in filtering , chemical in suffocation , ions in exchange , chemical in systematization it changes . It is physico-chemical processes slowly slowly theirs mechanic properties and permeability change can

Again processed of the material characteristics each different rains , atmosphere carbonization and atmosphere events effect does It was found that , in particular, laughing of materials to water active minerals ash piles and beds durability and consolidation effect shows. Ash slag of materials separately organize doers three to the group divided into : hydraulic activity according to and harden type according to To the first group high hydraulic to activity have and himself harden feature have minerals enters ; to the second - hydraulic which is low in activity the first group minerals when accelerating , and they are harden in the process together participation is enough ; to the third - hydraulic inert minerals , then even cementing agent ash slags , which in the composition himself harden minerals there is was , for example gypsum , free calcium pictures , pictures and sh.o '. With that together , cementing level , cemented ash of mass durability , maximum to strength reach period neither only minerals quantity with , to cement those who receive , but and another to factors such as their crushed , substances phase situations and etc Reclamation done sand slag collections xar different IES materials resilience indicators according to research the results analysis when done , the following designation possible : internal friction corner ph basically particles shape , humidity depending on (moisture how much less if so , to move has been resistance that's all big will be and vice versa). Ash piles flexibility their chemical and minerals composition , fractions recultivation done materials keep to the conditions dependent. Ash and of kulslaks strength and deformation features before reclamation done significant level difference does , that is , long the rest of

sediments resilience indicators τ and compressibility Y_e new reclamation of those made significant difference does Consolidation to the process , structure for preservation , as well of waste decomposition , metallurgy industry their waste physico-chemical - mechanical features the most a lot effect does Metallurgy of slag stability negative effect doer factors a lot in scores volume from growing up come coming out their to decay is a tendency . Positive properties by itself density and cementation enters Slags breakdown , rule according to , they of size two or three times increase and As a result structure strength to decrease take will come . To decay inclination basically SaO the to the amount dependent will be. Slag waste in assessment each one separately in case his age and chemical to the composition depends has been chemical of the structure stability determination need Marten stove of slag by itself decomposition , structure strength violation and in size expansion (swelling) in tissues usually one how many from the moon one how many up to continue reach can , therefore for decay process acceleration for new marten slugs 2-3 m layering , permanent water with watering stand up need it as a result of slag decomposition in 5...6 months face to give can

Time tooth with himself strengthening slag big piecemeal sand pieces himself to its consolidation similar as well as granulometric to the composition depends will be If the slag in collections to the colossus about dusts , forming grunt and the like if so , then in collections itself fortification process slows down and above of components any one superiority is determined .

In heaps by nature to decay of the inclined existence time during fortification and strengthening decrease processes queue with face to give take will come .

Mines rocks (from mines came out invalid genders heap), earth underground coals digging in getting formed and by itself to burn inclined , special from the content consists of will be. Coal mines main heap mass usually clays own into under the rock coals age (argillites , siltstones , clay cemented sandy) often of sulphides consists of will be. Erosion under the influence of the

sexes from the sun their durability decreases and breaks down , that is genders to decay take will come and active sensitive surface sharp to increase take will come . Time tooth with sensitive surface grows , of water existence them to get wet and in size to knayage take will come . Contains gills of the sexes in size expansion the amount change , %: for sands - from 0.15 to 2.1 ; siltstones for - from 3.4 to 7.5 ; argillites from 15.8 to 24 for . In size expansion genders strength to break and them colloidal chemical processes come to exit , which one active sensitive surfaces , absorption ability to increase take will come . Mine genders in hydration and his layer oxygen and carbonate anhydride acceptance it is up to a temperature of 55-70°C is heated , in which physical and chemical oxidation reaction accelerates and they are burning can By itself burning usually local to the character have , therefore for on fire often the stone left in heaps will be , partially on fire gone and yet fire untouched , heaps gender mass one different No. Mine rocks in waste there is has been flammable materials (coal , stones coal with mutually growth , coal slanes , various sulfur combinations) most of waste to burn take will come ; burning in the zone temperature 900 ... 1200°C. Himself to burn inclination mine gender chemical activity , structure to the density , itself density to the level , gralumatic to the composition depends Often himself of flammability hearth empty and dense of the sexes within the limit surface will come .

Mine genders himself flammability prevention get for genders decay reduce according to remedy events take to go hydration opportunity lose them clay grunts layer with close as well genders densification with to the sexes havan and humidity come in coming blocked , acidic atmosphere neutralizes. Organic to substances have has been don't pour in grunts - theirs disintegration face will give . Organic of the material decay intensity basically of grunt humidity and his change character , to them the air come in to go and another factors with is determined . Organic of substances disintegration the most intensive respectively

in humidity periodic changes happen It was good aeration and the like conditions when , less intensive - land under waters below the level of screens existence , ie . low filtration to the coefficient have soil layers , asphalt coating and others

REFERENCES:

- 1.QMQ 2.02.01-98. Bino va inshootlar zaminlari. – Toshkent, 2018
- 2.QMQ 2.01.07-97. Yuklar va ta`sirlar. – Toshkent, 2018.
- 3.Frolov N.N. Proektirovanie osnovaniy i fundamentov gidromeliorativnx soorujeniy. M.: Kolos, 2015.
- 4.Silkin A.M., Frolov N.N. Osnovaniya i fundament. M.: Kolos, 2017.
- 5.Tsitovich N.A. Mexanika gruntov. M.: Stroyizdat, 2013.
- 6.Rasulov X.Z. Gruntlar mexanikasi, zamin va poydevorlar. T.: O`qituvchi, 2013.
- 7.Ashrabov A.A., Zaytsev Yu.V. Qurilish konstruktsiyalari. T.: O`qituvchi, 2018.
- 8.Davronbek o`g`li, H. D., & Turgunboy o`g`li, Z. A. CONSTRUCTION OF GROUNDS AND FOUNDATIONS ON BULK SOIL.
- 9.Xasanov, D., & Xolmirzayev, Q. (2022). ECONOMIC FARM DESIGN. *Science and Innovation*, 1(4), 68-75.
- 10.Xasanov, D., & Xolmirzayev, Q. (2022). TEJAMKOR FERMA LARNI LOYIHALASH. *Science and innovation*, 1(A4), 68-75.
- 11.Бахромов, М., & Хасанов, Д. (2022). ТЎКМА ГРУНТЛАРДА ЗАМИН ВА ПОЙДЕВОРЛАР ҚУРИЛИШИ. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 2(6), 353-360.